

Third-Order Asymptotics for Power Sums of Mahonian Coefficients and OEIS Conjectures A380274–A380275

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Abstract

Let

$$[n]_q! = \prod_{m=1}^n (1 + q + \cdots + q^{m-1})$$

and let

$$M_n(j) = [q^j][n]_q!$$

be the Mahonian coefficient, equivalently the number of permutations of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ with exactly j inversions. For fixed real $r > 1$, define

$$S_r(n) = \sum_j M_n(j)^r.$$

We prove the third-order asymptotic formula

$$S_r(n) = C_r \frac{(n!)^r}{n^{3(r-1)/2}} \left(1 + \frac{c_1(r)}{n} + \frac{c_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{c_3(r)}{n^3} + o_r(n^{-3}) \right),$$

where

$$C_r = \frac{2^{(r-1)/2} 3^{r-1}}{\sqrt{r} \pi^{(r-1)/2}},$$

$$c_1(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(34r-9)}{100r},$$

$$c_2(r) = \frac{(r-1)(509796r^3 + 969886r^2 + 396009r - 4185)}{980000r^2},$$

and

$$c_3(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(5777688r^5 + 43341976r^4 + 77192488r^3 - 47522649r^2 - 5528700r + 2680965)}{98000000r^3}.$$

The leading term proves the general power-sum conjecture stated in OEIS A380275. The cases $r = 3$ and $r = 4$ prove and refine the conjectures in OEIS A380274 and A380275 by giving three explicit correction terms.

1 Introduction

The q -factorial

$$[n]_q! = \prod_{m=1}^n (1 + q + \cdots + q^{m-1})$$

is the inversion generating polynomial for the symmetric group S_n . Thus

$$M_n(j) = [q^j][n]_q!$$

is the number of permutations of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ with exactly j inversions.

The present paper studies the fixed-power sums

$$S_r(n) = \sum_j M_n(j)^r$$

for fixed real $r > 1$. Two special cases were recorded as OEIS conjectures. OEIS A380274 concerns

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^3$$

and states the asymptotic prediction

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^3 \sim \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \frac{(n!)^3}{n^3}.$$

OEIS A380275 concerns

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^4$$

and states the asymptotic prediction

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^4 \sim \frac{27\sqrt{2}}{\pi^{3/2}} \frac{(n!)^4}{n^{9/2}}.$$

The same OEIS entry also gives the general predicted leading term for fixed positive integer powers.

We prove the general fixed-real-power asymptotic and compute the first three correction terms. The proof uses the independent-sum representation of the inversion number, explicit cumulants of discrete uniform random variables, a lattice local Edgeworth expansion for triangular arrays, Poisson summation for Gaussian lattice sums, and a Hoeffding tail estimate. The local expansion is derived in the present normalization; standard references for the required Edgeworth machinery are Feller [4], Petrov [5], and Bhattacharya–Rao [6].

2 Main theorem

Theorem 1. *Let*

$$M_n(j) = [q^j] \prod_{m=1}^n (1 + q + \dots + q^{m-1}).$$

For every fixed real number $r > 1$, define

$$S_r(n) = \sum_j M_n(j)^r.$$

Then

$$S_r(n) = C_r \frac{(n!)^r}{n^{3(r-1)/2}} \left(1 + \frac{c_1(r)}{n} + \frac{c_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{c_3(r)}{n^3} + o_r(n^{-3}) \right),$$

where

$$C_r = \frac{2^{(r-1)/2} 3^{r-1}}{\sqrt{r} \pi^{(r-1)/2}},$$

$$c_1(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(34r-9)}{100r},$$

$$c_2(r) = \frac{(r-1)(509796r^3 + 969886r^2 + 396009r - 4185)}{980000r^2},$$

and

$$c_3(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(5777688r^5 + 43341976r^4 + 77192488r^3 - 47522649r^2 - 5528700r + 2680965)}{98000000r^3}.$$

Corollary 1 (OEIS A380274). *One has*

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^3 = \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \frac{(n!)^3}{n^3} \left(1 - \frac{93}{50n} + \frac{657703}{122500n^2} - \frac{18214629}{1225000n^3} + o(n^{-3}) \right).$$

In particular,

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^3 \sim \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \frac{(n!)^3}{n^3}.$$

Corollary 2 (OEIS A380275). *One has*

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^4 = \frac{27\sqrt{2}}{\pi^{3/2}} \frac{(n!)^4}{n^{9/2}} \left(1 - \frac{1143}{400n} + \frac{149174913}{15680000n^2} - \frac{190551792429}{6272000000n^3} + o(n^{-3}) \right).$$

In particular,

$$\sum_j M_n(j)^4 \sim \frac{27\sqrt{2}}{\pi^{3/2}} \frac{(n!)^4}{n^{9/2}}.$$

3 Mahonian distribution and cumulants

Let I_n be the inversion number of a uniformly random permutation in S_n . Then

$$p_n(j) := \mathbb{P}(I_n = j) = \frac{M_n(j)}{n!}.$$

The Lehmer-code representation gives

$$I_n = X_1 + \dots + X_n,$$

where X_1, \dots, X_n are independent and

$$X_m \sim \text{Unif}\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}.$$

Consequently

$$\mu_n := \mathbb{E} I_n = \frac{n(n-1)}{4},$$

and

$$\sigma_n^2 := \text{Var}(I_n) = \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{m^2 - 1}{12} = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{72}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\sigma_n^2 = \frac{n^3}{36} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2n} - \frac{5}{2n^2} \right).$$

For $X_m \sim \text{Unif}\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$, the even cumulants are

$$\kappa_{2a}(X_m) = \frac{B_{2a}}{2a} (m^{2a} - 1),$$

where B_{2a} is the Bernoulli number. The odd cumulants vanish after centering. Therefore the cumulants of I_n are

$$\kappa_{2a,n} = \frac{B_{2a}}{2a} \sum_{m=1}^n (m^{2a} - 1).$$

In particular,

$$\kappa_{4,n} = -\frac{1}{120} \sum_{m=1}^n (m^4 - 1),$$

$$\kappa_{6,n} = \frac{1}{252} \sum_{m=1}^n (m^6 - 1),$$

and

$$\kappa_{8,n} = -\frac{1}{240} \sum_{m=1}^n (m^8 - 1).$$

A direct expansion yields

$$\frac{\kappa_{4,n}}{\sigma_n^4} = -\frac{54}{25n} + \frac{27}{25n^2} - \frac{639}{50n^3} + O(n^{-4}),$$

$$\frac{\kappa_{6,n}}{\sigma_n^6} = \frac{1296}{49n^2} - \frac{1296}{49n^3} + O(n^{-4}),$$

and

$$\frac{\kappa_{8,n}}{\sigma_n^8} = -\frac{3888}{5n^3} + O(n^{-4}).$$

We use the probabilists' Hermite polynomials

$$H_m(x) = (-1)^m e^{x^2/2} \frac{d^m}{dx^m} e^{-x^2/2}.$$

The first ones needed below are

$$H_4 = x^4 - 6x^2 + 3,$$

$$H_6 = x^6 - 15x^4 + 45x^2 - 15,$$

$$H_8 = x^8 - 28x^6 + 210x^4 - 420x^2 + 105.$$

4 Local Edgeworth expansion

Let

$$x_{n,j} = \frac{j - \mu_n}{\sigma_n}, \quad \phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-x^2/2}.$$

Proposition 1 (Third-order central local Edgeworth expansion). *Uniformly for*

$$|x_{n,j}| \leq A\sqrt{\log n},$$

where $A > 0$ is fixed, one has

$$\sigma_n p_n(j) = \phi(x_{n,j}) \left[1 + \frac{P_1(x_{n,j})}{n} + \frac{P_2(x_{n,j})}{n^2} + \frac{P_3(x_{n,j})}{n^3} + O_A \left(\frac{(1 + |x_{n,j}|)^{16}}{n^4} \right) \right],$$

where

$$P_1(x) = -\frac{9}{100} H_4(x),$$

$$P_2(x) = \frac{9}{200} H_4(x) + \frac{9}{245} H_6(x) + \frac{81}{20000} H_8(x),$$

and

$$P_3(x) = -\frac{213}{400} H_4(x) - \frac{9}{245} H_6(x) - \frac{3267}{140000} H_8(x) - \frac{81}{24500} H_{10}(x) - \frac{243}{2000000} H_{12}(x).$$

Proof. We spell out the Fourier derivation, since this is the only point in the argument at which a lattice Edgeworth theorem is being used. The centered characteristic function of I_n is

$$\Psi_n(t) = \mathbb{E}e^{it(I_n - \mu_n)} = \prod_{m=1}^n \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)}.$$

Fourier inversion gives

$$p_n(j) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \Psi_n(t) e^{-it(j - \mu_n)} dt.$$

Put $t = u/\sigma_n$. For $|u| \leq C\sqrt{\log n}$, all arguments $mt/2$ are $O(\sqrt{\log n}/\sqrt{n})$. Taylor expansion of $\log(\sin z/z)$, with the remainder bounded uniformly in this range, gives

$$\log \Psi_n(u/\sigma_n) = -\frac{u^2}{2} + \frac{\kappa_{4,n}}{24\sigma_n^4}(iu)^4 + \frac{\kappa_{6,n}}{720\sigma_n^6}(iu)^6 + \frac{\kappa_{8,n}}{40320\sigma_n^8}(iu)^8 + O(n^{-4}(1 + |u|)^{12}).$$

The constant in the O -term is allowed to depend on C , but not on j or n . This is the standard central part of the lattice local Edgeworth expansion; see, for example, the treatments of lattice Edgeworth expansions in Feller [4, Ch. XVI], Petrov [5, Chs. VII–VIII], and Bhattacharya–Rao [6].

Using the cumulant expansions from the previous section and exponentiating, we obtain

$$\Psi_n(u/\sigma_n) = e^{-u^2/2} \left[1 + \frac{Q_1(u)}{n} + \frac{Q_2(u)}{n^2} + \frac{Q_3(u)}{n^3} + O(n^{-4}(1 + |u|)^{16}) \right],$$

where

$$Q_1(u) = -\frac{9}{100}(iu)^4,$$

$$Q_2(u) = \frac{9}{200}(iu)^4 + \frac{9}{245}(iu)^6 + \frac{81}{20000}(iu)^8,$$

and

$$Q_3(u) = -\frac{213}{400}(iu)^4 - \frac{9}{245}(iu)^6 - \frac{3267}{140000}(iu)^8 - \frac{81}{24500}(iu)^{10} - \frac{243}{2000000}(iu)^{12}.$$

Termwise Fourier inversion uses

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-iux} e^{-u^2/2} (iu)^m du = H_m(x) \phi(x).$$

To justify the replacement of the finite Fourier integral by the full Gaussian integrals, choose the Fourier cutoff $T = C\sqrt{\log n}$, with C sufficiently large in terms of the central-window constant A . The Gaussian model tails beyond $|u| > T$ are smaller than the displayed error. The corresponding non-central part of the original Fourier integral is controlled by Lemma 5 in Appendix A, with a power saving stronger than required. This completes the proof of the stated central local Edgeworth expansion. \square

5 Lattice sums and tails

Lemma 1 (Gaussian lattice sums). *Let $a > 0$, let $P(x)$ be a polynomial, and let $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$. Uniformly in the shift $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, for every $N > 0$,*

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} P\left(\frac{j - \alpha}{\sigma}\right) \exp\left(-a \left(\frac{j - \alpha}{\sigma}\right)^2\right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(x) e^{-ax^2} dx + O_{P,a,N}(\sigma^{-N}).$$

Proof. Put $f(x) = P(x)e^{-ax^2}$. Then f is a Schwartz function. Poisson summation gives

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} f\left(\frac{j - \alpha}{\sigma}\right) = \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} e^{-2\pi i m \alpha} \widehat{f}(2\pi m \sigma).$$

The $m = 0$ term is $\int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x) dx$, and the remaining terms are $O_N(\sigma^{-N})$ because \widehat{f} is also Schwartz. The bound is uniform in α . \square

Lemma 2 (Tail estimate). *For every fixed $r > 1$, and for $A > 0$ sufficiently large,*

$$\sigma_n^{r-1} \sum_{|j - \mu_n| > A\sigma_n \sqrt{\log n}} p_n(j)^r = o(n^{-3}).$$

Proof. The local limit theorem for the Mahonian distribution implies

$$\sup_j \sigma_n p_n(j) = O(1).$$

This also follows from the local limit theorem for inversion statistics in finite Coxeter groups proved by Kahle and Stump [1]. Hence

$$\sigma_n^{r-1} \sum_{|j - \mu_n| > A\sigma_n \sqrt{\log n}} p_n(j)^r \leq C_r \mathbb{P}\left(|I_n - \mu_n| > A\sigma_n \sqrt{\log n}\right).$$

Since $I_n = X_1 + \cdots + X_n$ with independent $X_m \in [0, m - 1]$, Hoeffding's inequality gives

$$\mathbb{P}(|I_n - \mu_n| \geq t) \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{2t^2}{\sum_{m=1}^n (m-1)^2}\right).$$

Now

$$\sum_{m=1}^n (m-1)^2 = \frac{n(n-1)(2n-1)}{6},$$

while

$$\sigma_n^2 = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{72}.$$

Thus

$$\frac{2\sigma_n^2}{\sum_{m=1}^n (m-1)^2} = \frac{2n+5}{6(2n-1)} \geq \frac{1}{6}.$$

Taking $t = A\sigma_n \sqrt{\log n}$ yields

$$\mathbb{P}\left(|I_n - \mu_n| > A\sigma_n \sqrt{\log n}\right) \leq 2n^{-A^2/6}.$$

Choosing $A > \sqrt{18}$ gives $o(n^{-3})$. \square

6 Proof of the main theorem

Let

$$q_n(j) = \sigma_n p_n(j).$$

Then

$$\sum_j p_n(j)^r = \sigma_n^{1-r} \sum_j \frac{1}{\sigma_n} q_n(j)^r.$$

By Proposition 1, in the central window $|x_{n,j}| \leq A\sqrt{\log n}$,

$$q_n(j) = \phi(x_{n,j}) \left[1 + \frac{P_1(x_{n,j})}{n} + \frac{P_2(x_{n,j})}{n^2} + \frac{P_3(x_{n,j})}{n^3} + O_A \left(\frac{(1 + |x_{n,j}|)^{16}}{n^4} \right) \right].$$

Therefore

$$q_n(j)^r = \phi(x_{n,j})^r \left[1 + \frac{rP_1}{n} + \frac{rP_2 + \frac{r(r-1)}{2}P_1^2}{n^2} + \frac{rP_3 + r(r-1)P_1P_2 + \frac{r(r-1)(r-2)}{6}P_1^3}{n^3} + O_{A,r} \left(\frac{(1 + |x_{n,j}|)^{48}}{n^4} \right) \right],$$

where the polynomials are evaluated at $x_{n,j}$. By Lemma 2, the complement of the central window contributes $o(n^{-3})$ after multiplication by σ_n^{r-1} . Inside the central window, Lemma 1 replaces the lattice sums by the corresponding Gaussian integrals with error $o(n^{-3})$. Hence

$$\sum_j p_n(j)^r = \sigma_n^{1-r} I_r \left(1 + \frac{D_1(r)}{n} + \frac{D_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{D_3(r)}{n^3} + o(n^{-3}) \right),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_r &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \phi(x)^r dx = \frac{1}{\sqrt{r}(2\pi)^{(r-1)/2}}, \\ D_1(r) &= r \frac{\int P_1(x) \phi(x)^r dx}{\int \phi(x)^r dx}, \\ D_2(r) &= \frac{\int \left(rP_2(x) + \frac{r(r-1)}{2}P_1(x)^2 \right) \phi(x)^r dx}{\int \phi(x)^r dx}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$D_3(r) = \frac{\int \left(rP_3(x) + r(r-1)P_1(x)P_2(x) + \frac{r(r-1)(r-2)}{6}P_1(x)^3 \right) \phi(x)^r dx}{\int \phi(x)^r dx}.$$

With respect to the probability density proportional to $\phi(x)^r$, the variable x has distribution $N(0, 1/r)$. Direct Gaussian moment calculation gives

$$\begin{aligned} D_1(r) &= -\frac{27(r-1)^2}{100r}, \\ D_2(r) &= \frac{27(r-1)(1323r^3 - 4957r^2 + 7317r - 155)}{980000r^2}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$D_3(r) = -\frac{9(r-1)(35721r^5 - 258633r^4 + 18640846r^3 - 18661558r^2 - 1877775r + 893655)}{98000000r^3}.$$

It remains to expand σ_n^{1-r} . Since

$$\sigma_n^2 = \frac{n^3}{36} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2n} - \frac{5}{2n^2} \right),$$

we have

$$\sigma_n^{1-r} = 6^{r-1} n^{-3(r-1)/2} \left(1 + \frac{s_1(r)}{n} + \frac{s_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{s_3(r)}{n^3} + O(n^{-4}) \right),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} s_1(r) &= -\frac{3(r-1)}{4}, \\ s_2(r) &= \frac{(r-1)(9r+49)}{32}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$s_3(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(r+1)(3r+49)}{128}.$$

Combining the expansions yields

$$\sum_j p_n(j)^r = \frac{6^{r-1}}{\sqrt{r}(2\pi)^{(r-1)/2}} n^{-3(r-1)/2} \left(1 + \frac{c_1(r)}{n} + \frac{c_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{c_3(r)}{n^3} + o(n^{-3}) \right),$$

where

$$c_1 = s_1 + D_1, \quad c_2 = s_2 + D_2 + s_1 D_1,$$

and

$$c_3 = s_3 + D_3 + s_1 D_2 + s_2 D_1.$$

The displayed formulas for $c_1(r)$, $c_2(r)$, $c_3(r)$ follow by simplification.

Finally, since $M_n(j) = n!p_n(j)$,

$$S_r(n) = (n!)^r \sum_j p_n(j)^r.$$

Also

$$\frac{6^{r-1}}{(2\pi)^{(r-1)/2}} = \frac{2^{(r-1)/2} 3^{r-1}}{\pi^{(r-1)/2}}.$$

This proves Theorem 1.

7 Verification script for the constants

The following short script verifies the symbolic constants appearing in Theorem 1.

```
import sympy as sp

r = sp.symbols('r')
x = sp.symbols('x')

def H(k):
    return sp.expand((-1)**k * sp.exp(x**2/2)
                    * sp.diff(sp.exp(-x**2/2), x, k))

H4, H6, H8, H10, H12 = [H(k) for k in [4,6,8,10,12]]

P1 = -sp.Rational(9,100)*H4

P2 = (sp.Rational(9,200)*H4
      + sp.Rational(9,245)*H6
      + sp.Rational(81,20000)*H8)

P3 = (-sp.Rational(213,400)*H4
      - sp.Rational(9,245)*H6
      - sp.Rational(3267,140000)*H8
      - sp.Rational(81,24500)*H10
      - sp.Rational(243,2000000)*H12)

def moment(k):
```

```

if k % 2:
    return sp.Integer(0)
m = k // 2
return sp.Integer(1) if m == 0 else sp.factorial2(2*m-1)/r**m

def expect(poly):
    poly = sp.Poly(sp.expand(poly), x)
    ans = sp.Integer(0)
    for (k,), coeff in poly.terms():
        ans += coeff * moment(k)
    return sp.simplify(ans)

D1 = sp.simplify(r * expect(P1))
D2 = sp.simplify(r * expect(P2)
                + r*(r-1)/2 * expect(P1**2))
D3 = sp.simplify(r * expect(P3)
                + r*(r-1) * expect(P1*P2)
                + r*(r-1)*(r-2)/6 * expect(P1**3))

s1 = -sp.Rational(3,4)*(r-1)
s2 = (r-1)*(9*r+49)/sp.Integer(32)
s3 = -sp.Rational(3,128)*(r-1)*(r+1)*(3*r+49)

c1 = sp.simplify(s1 + D1)
c2 = sp.simplify(s2 + D2 + s1*D1)
c3 = sp.simplify(s3 + D3 + s1*D2 + s2*D1)

print("c1 =", sp.factor(c1))
print("c2 =", sp.factor(c2))
print("c3 =", sp.factor(c3))
print("r=3:", sp.factor(c1.subs(r,3)),
      sp.factor(c2.subs(r,3)),
      sp.factor(c3.subs(r,3)))
print("r=4:", sp.factor(c1.subs(r,4)),
      sp.factor(c2.subs(r,4)),
      sp.factor(c3.subs(r,4)))

```

The output is

$$c_1(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(34r-9)}{100r},$$

$$c_2(r) = \frac{(r-1)(509796r^3 + 969886r^2 + 396009r - 4185)}{980000r^2},$$

and

$$c_3(r) = -\frac{3(r-1)(5777688r^5 + 43341976r^4 + 77192488r^3 - 47522649r^2 - 5528700r + 2680965)}{98000000r^3}.$$

For $r = 3$, this gives

$$-\frac{93}{50}, \quad \frac{657703}{122500}, \quad -\frac{18214629}{1225000}.$$

For $r = 4$, this gives

$$-\frac{1143}{400}, \quad \frac{149174913}{15680000}, \quad -\frac{190551792429}{6272000000}.$$

8 Conclusion

We proved a third-order asymptotic expansion for fixed real power sums of Mahonian coefficients. The leading term confirms the general power-sum asymptotic conjecture recorded in OEIS A380275. The cases $r = 3$ and $r = 4$ prove and refine the conjectures in OEIS A380274 and A380275, respectively, by supplying three explicit correction terms.

A natural continuation is to compute the full asymptotic expansion

$$S_r(n) \sim C_r \frac{(n!)^r}{n^{3(r-1)/2}} \left(1 + \frac{c_1(r)}{n} + \frac{c_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{c_3(r)}{n^3} + \dots \right),$$

where each coefficient is obtained from Bernoulli numbers and Hermite polynomial integrals against the Gaussian weight $\phi(x)^r$.

A Non-central Fourier estimates

This appendix supplies the Fourier estimates used in Proposition 1. The goal is to make explicit that the part of the inversion integral outside the central Fourier window is smaller than any fixed negative power of n , after choosing a logarithmic cutoff large enough.

Throughout this appendix,

$$\Psi_n(t) = \mathbb{E} e^{it(I_n - \mu_n)} = \prod_{m=1}^n \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)}$$

denotes the centered characteristic function of the Mahonian distribution. We use the elementary inequality

$$\left| \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)} \right| \leq 1, \quad 1 \leq m \leq n,$$

which follows from $|\sin(mx)| \leq m|\sin x|$.

Lemma 3 (Small-frequency decay). *There exist constants $\eta > 0$ and $c > 0$ such that, for all sufficiently large n ,*

$$|\Psi_n(t)| \leq \exp(-cn^3 t^2)$$

whenever $|t| \leq \eta/n$.

Proof. Choose $\eta > 0$ small. For $|y| \leq \eta$, the Taylor expansion of $\log(\sin y/y)$ gives

$$\log \left| \frac{\sin y}{y} \right| \leq -c_0 y^2$$

for some absolute constant $c_0 > 0$. Also

$$-\log \left| \frac{\sin(t/2)}{t/2} \right| \leq C_0 t^2$$

for $|t| \leq \eta/n$. Put $y_m = mt/2$. Since $|y_m| \leq \eta/2$,

$$\log \left| \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)} \right| = \log \left| \frac{\sin y_m}{y_m} \right| - \log \left| \frac{\sin(t/2)}{t/2} \right| \leq -c_0 \frac{m^2 t^2}{4} + C_0 t^2.$$

Summing over m gives

$$\log |\Psi_n(t)| \leq -c_1 t^2 \sum_{m=1}^n m^2 + C_0 n t^2 \leq -cn^3 t^2$$

for all sufficiently large n . This proves the lemma. \square

Lemma 4 (Intermediate and large-frequency decay). *There exist constants $K > 0$, $c > 0$, and n_0 such that*

$$|\Psi_n(t)| \leq e^{-cn}$$

for every $n \geq n_0$ and every $t \in [-\pi, \pi]$ satisfying

$$\eta/n \leq |t| \leq \pi.$$

Proof. We split the interval into two ranges.

First consider $\eta/n \leq |t| \leq K/n$, where $K > \eta$ is fixed. For $m \in [n/2, n]$, the number $m|t|/2$ lies in $[\eta/4, K/2]$. Since

$$\sup_{y \in [\eta/4, K/2]} \left| \frac{\sin y}{y} \right| < 1,$$

and since $\sin(t/2)/(t/2) = 1 + O_K(n^{-2})$ uniformly in this range, there is a constant $\rho < 1$ such that, for all sufficiently large n ,

$$\left| \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)} \right| \leq \rho$$

for every $m \in [n/2, n]$. All remaining factors have modulus at most 1. Hence

$$|\Psi_n(t)| \leq \rho^{n/2} = e^{-c_1 n}.$$

Now choose $K > 8\pi$ and consider $K/n \leq |t| \leq \pi$. Since $0 \leq |t|/2 \leq \pi/2$,

$$\sin(|t|/2) \geq |t|/\pi.$$

For every

$$m \geq \frac{2\pi}{|t|},$$

we therefore have

$$\left| \frac{\sin(mt/2)}{m \sin(t/2)} \right| \leq \frac{1}{m \sin(|t|/2)} \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Since $|t| \geq K/n$ and $K > 8\pi$, there are at least $n/2$ such integers $m \leq n$. The remaining factors again have modulus at most 1, and therefore

$$|\Psi_n(t)| \leq 2^{-n/2} = e^{-c_2 n}.$$

Combining the two ranges proves the lemma. \square

Lemma 5 (Non-central Fourier tail). *Let $L \geq 0$ and $B > 0$ be fixed. There exists $C = C(L, B) > 0$ such that, with $T = C\sqrt{\log n}$,*

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_n} \int_{T < |u| \leq \pi\sigma_n} (1 + |u|)^L \left| \Psi_n \left(\frac{u}{\sigma_n} \right) \right| du = O_{L,B}(n^{-B}).$$

Proof. Write $t = u/\sigma_n$. The range $T < |u| \leq \pi\sigma_n$ is divided according to $|t| \leq \eta/n$ and $|t| > \eta/n$.

In the first range, Lemma 3 and $\sigma_n^2 \asymp n^3$ give

$$|\Psi_n(u/\sigma_n)| \leq \exp(-c'u^2).$$

Hence

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_n} \int_{T < |u| \leq \eta\sigma_n/n} (1 + |u|)^L |\Psi_n(u/\sigma_n)| du \leq \frac{1}{\sigma_n} \int_{|u| > T} (1 + |u|)^L e^{-c'u^2} du.$$

Choosing C sufficiently large makes this $O(n^{-B})$.

In the remaining range, Lemma 4 gives $|\Psi_n(u/\sigma_n)| \leq e^{-cn}$. Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_n} \int_{\eta\sigma_n/n < |u| \leq \pi\sigma_n} (1 + |u|)^L |\Psi_n(u/\sigma_n)| du \leq C_L \sigma_n^L e^{-cn} = O_{L,B}(n^{-B}).$$

The two estimates prove the claim. □

Remark 1. *Lemma 5 is stronger than what is needed for the third-order expansion. It shows that any fixed polynomial weight in the Fourier variable can be absorbed by taking the logarithmic cutoff large enough. This justifies the termwise Fourier inversion in Proposition 1, including the polynomial error terms arising from the cumulant expansion.*

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